

MODELING OF ADHESIVE LAYERS OF LAMINATED PLATES IN DELAMINATION SIMULATION

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SUMMARY

This paper first briefly reviews the interface elements based on penalty contacts for delamination simulations of laminated plates. Then it presents a new 3-D interface element based on solid-shell element for delamination simulation. Numerical examples show that the solid-shell interface element is efficient and accurate for delamination simulations.

Keywords: *laminated plates, impact damage, delamination simulation, interfacial layer modeling, solid-shell interface element*

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced laminated plates and shells possess high specific modulus and high specific strength in the reinforcement direction, and they are widely used in various industries, such as aerospace, automobile, ship building, construction etc. However, the transverse strength of laminated plates is very weak, especially at the adhesive layers which are the resin rich zones at the interlaminar interfaces. As a result, laminated plates will suffer damages, such as matrix cracking, debonding and inter-ply delaminations, when they are under the action of the low-velocity transverse impact [1-3]. Among these impact induced damages, the delamination at the interlaminar interfaces with different fiber orientations is the most dangerous one as it can severely affect the strength and stability of the damaged laminates. The numerical simulation based on the finite element method is a powerful tool for the prediction of delaminations of laminated plates subjected to low velocity impact. The key issue in the delamination simulation is the behaviour modelling of the interfacial layers of the laminated plates. In recently years, many interface elements were proposed for the modeling of the interfacial layers [4-9] either for the 2-D shell element models or for the 3-D element models. These interface elements, including the cohesive zone model, are based on the penalty contact approach [2, 3, 7 among others], in which the virtual contact springs and virtual relative displacements are used. The virtual contact springs have given penalty stiffness parameters to simulate a real connection between two neighbouring layers before delamination initiation. Nevertheless, the determination of spring stiffness for the penalty stiffness of the interfaces is not based on the physics of the adhesive layers, but rather arbitrary which leads to some numerical difficulty and instability [5-6]. In these models, the onset of the delaminations is controlled by the strength based criteria, and the delamination propagation is governed by means of the indirect use of fracture

mechanics. Various material models for the virtual springs of penalty contacts have been proposed so far [5, 10], but these models have some difficulties to accurately model the inter-ply delaminations with the interaction of the mixed modes of fractures.

Although the penalty contact-based interface elements are able to simulate the inter-ply delamination reasonably well, the accuracy and stability of the simulation results strongly depends on the users' good experience on the choice of the virtual spring stiffness [5-6]. Therefore, it is desirable to develop new efficient 3-D interface elements based on the real physics and geometry of the interfacial layer properties for the robust delamination simulations.

The objectives of this paper are two-folded. First, this paper briefly reviews the interface elements used in the numerical predictions of inter-ply delaminations of composite plates subjected to low velocity transverse impact. Second, a solid-shell element-based [11] interface element accounting for the real geometry and the material properties of the interfacial layers is proposed for the delamination simulation. The preliminary numerical study shows that the new 3-D interface element presented here is not only accurate, but also computationally efficient compared to the conventional 3-D interface elements in the delamination simulations of laminates plates.

ON THE INTERFACE ELEMENTS BASED ON PENALTY CONTACTS

When a laminated plate is subjected to low velocity transverse impacts, it will suffer delamination damage at the interlaminar layers. Because of the abrupt changes in stiffness at the adhesive layers of laminae with different fiber orientations, the inter-ply delamination would most likely take place along the adhesive layers bonding laminae with different fiber orientations. Therefore, the adhesive layers between the laminae having different fiber orientations can be modeled as the interfacial layers of laminated plates. A typical interfacial layer between two laminae is depicted in Fig. 1a. The adhesive layer has a finite thickness h_a , but it is much thinner than those of laminae.

Figure 1. Typical interfacial layer and penalty contact based interface element

In recently years, many interface elements bases on the concept of the cohesive zone model have been proposed for the behavior modeling of the interfacial layers of laminated plates either for the 2-D shell element models or for the 3-D element models [2, 3, 7]. The basic idea in these interface elements is the penalty contact for the cohesive zones, in which the stiffness of the virtual contact springs is used as penalty parameters to simulate a real connection between two neighboring layers before delamination as shown in Fig. 1b. There are two characteristic parameters in the penalty

contact based interface models depicted in Fig. 1b, one is the stiffness of the virtual spring k , and other is the virtual thickness of the interface h_{gap} . However, the determination of spring stiffness and the thickness of the interface elements in these models are not based on the physics and geometry of the adhesive layers, but rather arbitrary. For instance, $h_{gap} = 0$ is used in some interface models [1, 3-5, 10], but a finite value in terms of a fraction of lamina thickness for h_{gap} , not the real thickness of the interfacial layer i.e. $h_{gap} \neq h_a$, is defined in other models [7-9]. The value of h_{gap} in some delamination simulations can be dozens of times larger than the real thickness of adhesive layers. For example one-fifth of the lamina thickness for h_{gap} was suggested in Ref. 7. Because of such nature of the penalty contact based interface models, the resulting interface elements could lead to some numerical difficulty and instability [5].

The basic field variables of interface elements based on the penalty contact are the tractions of the virtual springs \mathbf{p} and the relative displacements $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ between the neighboring laminae, $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ can be treated as the equivalent crack opening displacements for delamination of laminated composite structures. Before the delaminations take place, the relation between the tractions \mathbf{p} and the relative displacements $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ at an interface can be defined as

$$\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\delta} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{D} is the stiffness matrix of virtual springs for the interfaces. The relative displacements $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ and stiffness matrix \mathbf{D} take the following forms respectively

$$\boldsymbol{\delta} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta_1 \\ \delta_2 \\ \delta_3 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{Bmatrix}_{top} - \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{Bmatrix}_{bottom}, \quad \mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & k_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2-3)$$

In the penalty stiffness based interface models, the delamination damage is supposed to be initiated when the maximum traction reaches a threshold, and then the stiffness of contact springs is degraded. Various softening laws of the spring stiffness were proposed so far [5, 10]. The bilinear constitutive law for the virtual spring is the most popular one. A bilinear constitutive law is illustrated in Fig. 2, Fig. 2a is the force-displacement curve, Fig. 2b shows the equivalent strain energy release rate of the spring where G_i ($i = I, II, III$), the area of the triangle OAB, is the strain energy release rate of crack mode i ($i = I, II, III$) and G_{iC} , the total area of the triangle OAC, is the corresponding critical strain energy release rate. As shown Fig. 2, the strength based criteria is used to control the onset of the interfacial damages, and the indirect use of fracture mechanics is adopted to determine the delamination propagation, in which the energy dissipated in the virtual spring is equivalent to the strain energy release rate in fracture mechanics [1, 3, 5-7, 10]. In case of mixed crack modes of fracture, various power laws are widely used to approximate the interaction of the three fracture modes. However, the model of power laws is not easy to accurately predict the delaminations associated to the mixed cracks modes of fractures since the crack propagation direction depends not only on the stress regime at the crack tip but also on the ply orientation adjacent to the crack plane [1].

Figure 2. A bilinear constitutive law for the virtual springs

The advantage of these interface models is the simplicity and the unification of damage initiation and delamination propagation. The disadvantage is that the accuracy, efficiency even stability of delamination simulations strongly depend on the proper choice of the value of the spring stiffness. Unfortunately, the determination of proper values of the spring stiffness is totally based on the users' expertises, as small values of spring stiffness would induce large interpenetrations at the interfaces which are incompatible with the physical reality, and too large values of spring stiffness could produce numerical errors related to the computing accuracy [5-6].

NEW 3-D INTERFACE ELEMENT BASED ON SOLID-SHELL ELEMENT

The numerical simulation results have shown that the interface elements based on the penalty contact and the equivalence of dissipated energy to the energy release rate are capable of simulating the inter-ply delamination reasonably well. Nevertheless, Because the characteristic parameters in these interface elements are not the real properties of the adhesive layers, the accuracy and efficiency of the simulation results strongly depends on the users' good guess of the virtual spring stiffness. Therefore, it is desirable to develop some new interface elements based on the real physics and geometry of the interfacial layer properties for the robust delamination simulations.

The interfacial layers are the resin rich zones with finite thickness, and they can be modeled by 3-D elements theoretically. However, since the thickness of the interfacial layer is too thin compared with the thickness of the adjacent laminas, the mesh density of simulation model using the conventional 3-D interface elements is totally controlled by the suitable aspect ratio of the interface elements representing the thin adhesive layers. Consequently, the 3-D element modeling for the interfacial layers based on the conventional formulation leads to the resulting mesh being too large to be computationally practical [3]. The recently developed solid-shell element [11] is a type of special solid elements. The special features of solid-shell elements is that it has the 3-D geometry like the conventional solid elements, but it is also capable of modeling plate-like structures like plate elements and giving accurate results even in the case of large aspect ratios of length to thickness approaching to 100 [11]. Therefore, the computational inefficiency of the conventional 3-D interface element model can be overcome by the 3-D modeling of interfacial layers using the solid-shell elements. In addition, the real material properties and the physical thickness of the interfacial layers can be used directly in the solid-shell interface elements, and the damage mechanics can

also be directly employed rather than the indirect use of the fracture mechanics as the situation in the popular interface elements based on the penalty contact approach. The 3-D modeling for the interface layers using the solid-shell element is schematically shown in Fig.3. The new version of ANSYS added the solid-shell element into its element library [12]. The performance of the solid-shell elements in ANSYS 12.0 is evaluated in this study first, then a 3-D interface element based on the solid-shell element and the damage mechanics is proposed.

Figure 3. 3-D interface element based on solid-shell element formulation

The adhesive layer is the resin rich zone with thickness h_a . Consequently interface representing the adhesive layer can be treated as isotropic material with Young's modulus E_a and shear modulus G_a of the adhesive layer. Since the interfacial layers shown in Fig. 3 is modeled as a solid medium with a finite thickness h_a , the damage of the interfacial layers resulting from impacts can be modeled directly by the continuum damage mechanics. A general normal stress-strain curve of adhesive layer is shown in Fig. 4, where E_a^d denotes the Young's modulus of the damaged material and ε_{au} is the ultimate strain.

Figure 4. Material modeling of adhesive layers

Since the delamination patterns of interfacial layers are similar to the three crack modes of fractures, the interfacial delamination damages can be characterized by three damage parameters d_{a3} , d_{a1-12} and d_{a2-12} representing the interface damage, respectively, in the x_3 -direction, the x_1 -direction of the x_1-x_2 plane and the x_2 -direction of the x_1-x_2 plane as shown in Fig. 5. The damage parameters d_{a3} , d_{a1-12} and d_{a2-12} are the

functions of material properties E_a , G_a , σ_{as} and τ_{as} of adhesive layers and some internal variables. The progressive damage process of the inter-ply delamination induced by low-velocity impact can be modeled by a proper damage evolution law which is widely used in the continuum damage mechanics [13]. The area of under curve OAB in Fig. 4 is the strain energy density up to the failure. It can be seen from Fig. 4 that when the ultimate strain ε_{au} is a few times larger than ε_{ae} , ε_{au} can be used for the criterion of damage propagation.

Figure 5. The damage modeling of interfacial layer

DELAMINATION ANALYSIS USING SOLID-SHELL INTERFACE ELEMENT

The performance of the solid-shell interface element presented in the previous section is evaluated first in this section, then it is used for the simulation of the standard test of the double cantilevered beam to demonstrate the efficiency and accuracy of the solid-shell interface element.

Validation of solid-shell element in ANSYS

The deformation of [0/90/90/0] laminated beam under a uniform load q but with different boundary conditions are analyzed first to validate the accuracy of the solid-shell elements in laminated beam analysis. The material properties and the geometry of the beam are as following:

$$E_1 = 144.8\text{GPa}, E_2 = 9.65\text{GPa}, G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.14\text{GPa}, G_{23} = 3.45\text{GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.3$$

$$L = 103.75\text{mm}, h = 1.0375\text{mm}, h_l = 0.25\text{mm}, h_a = 0.0125\text{mm}$$

where $h_l = 0.25\text{mm}$ is the thickness of lamina. The aspect ratio of the beam $L/h = 100$.

100 elements are used along the beam axis direction, and each lamina is modeled by 4 layers of 3-D element SOLID45 in ANSYS, which result in that the aspect ratio α_{lr} of length l_{le} to thickness h_{le} for the elements used for laminae is $\alpha_{lr} = \frac{l_{le}}{h_{le}} = 16.6$. The

adhesive layer is modeled by the solid-shell element SOLSH190 in ANSYS, but different number of element layers is used for adhesive layers to study the influence of

the aspect ratio $\alpha_{ar} = \frac{l_{ae}}{h_{ae}}$ of element SOLSH190 on the analysis results, where l_{ae} is the interface element length and h_{ae} is the interface element thickness. The nondimensional maximum deflection the beam is defined as:

$$\bar{w} = w_{\max} \frac{E_2 b h^3 / 12}{q L^4}$$

The maximum deflections of the laminated beams with four different boundary conditions are tabulated in Table 1, where symbols for the boundary conditions are:

CC stands for Clamped – Clamped beam ends,

CF for Clamped – Free beam ends,

CS for Clamped – Simply supported beam ends,

SS for Simply supported – Simply supported beam ends.

The solutions given by the composite beam element HQCB-8A [14], which is based on higher-order shear deformation theory and the assumed strain method, is also listed in the table for comparison. But the adhesive layer is not considered in the analysis of HQCB-8A. The results in Table 1 show that the solid-shell interface elements deliver good results even when the aspect ratio α_{ae} of the interface elements is very large.

Table 1. Nondimensional maximum deflections given by solid-shell interface elements

layers of interface elements	aspect ratio α_{ar}	CC	CF	CS	SS
1	83	0.02107	0.99395	0.04343	0.10374
3	249	0.02107	0.99395	0.04343	0.10374
5	332	0.02107	0.99395	0.04343	0.10374
10	830	0.02123	0.99475	0.04359	0.10374
HQCB – 8A [14]		0.01998	0.94970	0.04113	0.09738

Crack propagation of DCB

The double cantilevered beam (DCB) considered here is schematically shown in Fig. 6. The geometry of DCB are the length of the beam $l=100mm$, height $h=3mm$, width $b=1mm$, initial crack length $a_0=30mm$, the thickness of adhesive layer $h_a=0.02mm$. The material properties of the laminae [7] are:

$$E_1=126\text{GPa}, E_2=E_3=7.5\text{GPa}, G_{12}=G_{13}=4.98\text{GPa}, G_{23}=3.28\text{GPa}, \nu_{12}=\nu_{13}=0.261$$

The adhesive layer are modeled as an isotropic material with material properties:

$$E_a=7.5\text{GPa}, G_a=3.28\text{GPa}, \sigma_{as}=57\text{MPa}, \varepsilon_{au}=0.015$$

The DCB shown in Fig. 6 can be considered as a laminated beam made of two laminae with an adhesive layer of 70mm long. 4 layers of solid elements are used for each lamina of the composite beam, and one layer of solid-shell element SOLSH190 are used for the adhesive layer of the beam as shown in Fig. 7a.

Figure 6. DCB with initial crack length $a_0=30\text{mm}$

Three element mesh densities are used for the adhesive layer, and finer meshes are used around the crack tip. The interfacial element lengths at the cohesive zone are respectively, $l_{ae} = 0.1\text{mm}$, 0.2mm and 0.5mm , and the corresponding aspect ratios are

$$\alpha_{ar} = \frac{l_{ae}}{h_{ae}} = 5, 10 \text{ and } 25. \text{ The finite element mesh with } l_{ae} = 0.2\text{mm} \text{ at the crack tip and}$$

the deformation shape of DCB at $F = 80\text{N}$ (before the peak load shown in Fig. 8) is depicted in Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b respectively.

(a) mesh at the crack tip

(b) deformation at $F = 80\text{N}$

Figure 7. Mesh at the crack tip and simulated crack opening of DCB

The force-opening displacement curves obtained by using the solid-shell interface element are illustrated in Fig. 8. It can be seen from the figure that the present results are agree well with the experimental results [7] when the interface element length $l_{ae} \leq 0.2\text{mm}$, this is because that the crack propagation is simulated by the material failure of the interface elements, and the propagation rate of the crack is controlled by the length l_{ae} of interface elements used to model the adhesive layers.

Figure 8. Simulation results of DCB given by solid-shell interface elements

The results in Table 1 and Fig. 8 have illustrated that the interface element based on the solid-shell element is a good method to model the interfacial layers of laminated structures which is extremely thin compared with those of neighbouring laminae but having a finite thickness.

CONCLUSIONS

Having reviewed the interface elements based on the penalty contacts, an interface element based on the solid-shell element is presented for the interfacial layer modeling in the delamination simulations of laminates plates. The preliminary numerical study shows that the present 3-D interface element based on the solid-shell element has the following advantages.

1. The real geometry of the interfacial layers of laminae, which are the resin rich zones between laminae, can be accurately modeled by the 3-D geometry of the solid-shell interface elements;
2. The real material properties of the adhesive layers can be used directly for the material modeling of the solid-shell interface element, and the damage and the failure of the interfacial layers can be characterized by damage mechanics rather than the indirect use of fracture mechanics;
3. The solid-shell interface element is computationally efficient for the modeling of extremely thin adhesive layers in laminated plates since the solid-shell element is also capable of giving good results in the case of large aspect ratio of element length to its height.

Therefore, the solid-shell interface element is an efficient numerical tool to model the behaviour of the thin interfacial layers in the delamination simulations of laminated structures.

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